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Site visit check list and report outline

WP 11. Combining HBM, health studies and registers

Version: 12 November 2019

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1 Authors and Acknowledgements

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2 Use and objectives

Site visits, sometimes also called audit visits, are part of the quality assurance process of field studies. Their aim is to evaluate how well provided standardized protocols are followed in different circumstances, cultures and infrastructures. In case of combined human biomonitoring (HBM) and health studies in Europe, this refers to the standardized protocol for combined HBM-HES study prepared under HBM4EU¹. This combined protocol is based on standardized operating protocols (SOPs) for human biomonitoring measures proposed by HBM4EU and protocols by European Health Examination Survey (EHES) for health measurements.

The purpose of a site visit is to document observations during an evaluation visit to a fieldwork site, including observations of possible deviations from European level standards. In general, two different levels of deviations may be observed:

1. Even though a European level protocol exists and countries are expected to use it, deviations may exist due to national adaptations. There are generally good reasons for these adaptations such as follow-up of trends from the previous national studies or financial limitations.
2. It may also be, that survey organizers have prepared their local study protocol following the European level standardized protocols but fieldwork staff is not following the protocol which results in deviations from it.

In the framework of HBM4EU, site visits will provide information about the comparability of survey methods used in different studies.

Site visits should be conducted by someone who is not involved in the preparation or conduction of the survey but knows well the European level standardized protocols from HBM4EU and EHES. In an ideal case, a site visit takes two days. During the first day, the fieldwork is monitored. If possible, at least a few real examinations and interviews are followed up with the consent from the survey participant and fieldwork staff. The observer is not allowed to intervene in the examination at any point or to comment the procedure while the survey participant is present. If allowed by the survey participant and fieldwork staff, photos can be taken to document the procedures. For photos, a written consent is required (see example template in Annex 1).

During the evaluation of the fieldwork, at least the following issues should be observed and documented:

- How easy it is to find the examination site and to access it?
- How the informed consent is obtained?
- How the privacy of the participants is ensured?
- How questionnaire(s) is/are administered?
- How each health measurement is conducted and which type of measurement devices are used as well as checking and calibration of devices?
- How biological samples are collected and handled on the field?
- How data protection on the field is ensured?
- How staff members interact and communicate with each other?

¹ Deliverable 11.1 Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies. Available at: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Deliverable-11.1-Report-on-opportunities-and-obstacles-of-combining-HBM-and-health-studies-availability-of-health-studies-with-biological-samples-availability-of-administrative-registers-and-guidelines-for-combining-HBM-and-health-studies.pdf>

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During the second day, observations from the first day should be discussed with the survey coordination team. During these discussions, reasons for observed deviations from the standardized protocols should be obtained and documented. The basis for the evaluation is the written study protocol which should include detailed description of the study and standardized operating procedures for specific measurements. Sometimes national study protocols cannot be shared due to confidentiality or they may be prepared in national language(s) and not always translated to English. Therefore, following topics should be discussed with the coordination team to obtain a comprehensive picture about the entire survey process:

- How much time and what kind of resources were needed for the planning and preparation of the survey?
- Process of obtaining ethical approval and, if applicable, approval by data protection authority.
- Fieldwork personnel
 - How fieldwork personnel were recruited? Were there any specific requirements to take into account during the recruitment?
 - How the survey personnel were trained?
 - How many survey teams are simultaneously working on the field and what is their composition?
- How the survey examination sites were selected?
- Sample selection
 - Which sampling frames were used and why?
 - How the sample size was determined?
 - How the sample was selected?
- How different modules for the used questionnaire(s) were selected? Was there any need for compromises to keep the participant's burden reasonable?
- How included health measurements were selected?
- How the biomarkers and chemicals to be measured were selected?
- What kind of national/survey specific quality control actions were used for the survey?
- Recruitment process of survey participants.
- How the fieldwork logistics were organized? Transfer of goods and samples between locations.
- How the data management is organized? How data confidentiality and protection is taken into account?
- What kind of dissemination plan the survey has?
- General discussion about encountered difficulties and success stories (what has worked well, what have been the biggest challenges).

To properly document the outcomes of the site visit, a written report should be prepared. This report is usually confidential between evaluators and survey organizers since it may contain non-public information about survey preparation, photos of survey participants in compromising situations and critical comments related to the conduct of the survey. Confidentiality of the report ensures that all, also critical issues are documented and properly discussed. Survey organizers are asked to share the report and final outcomes of the evaluation with the fieldwork staff. Required corrective measures should be taken or possible re-training of the fieldwork staff should be organized by the survey organizer whenever necessary. If both parties agree and there is no compromising information in the site visit report, it can also be made publicly available and thereby, serve as an example for other similar surveys of how things could be conducted.

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3 Site visit check list

The following check lists by topic can be used during the site visit to ensure that the relevant issues are evaluated. This is not a comprehensive list and whenever needed, survey specific features should be added. For example, the current list does not include all the potential clinical health examinations or collection of all possible types of biological samples which may be included in the survey.

During the site visit, it is recommended to take notes on more detailed observations and not only fill in this check list. These notes will provide in depth understanding of situation and should be summarized in a written site visit report.

3.1 Day one: Fieldwork evaluation

During the first day, the fieldwork is observed with the consent of the survey participants involved and that of fieldwork staff members. Following points are based on observations during the fieldwork.

3.1.1 Examination site

Was the examination site easy to locate? Yes
 No

Would the examination site be easy to access by a person with functional limitation (walking difficulties, use of wheel chair)? Yes
 No

Were there good, clear signs guiding to the examination site? Yes
 No

Did the premises permit privacy for the participant during the examinations and/or interview (soundproofing of the rooms etc.)? Yes
 No

3.1.2 Obtaining informed consent

Was the information material provided to the survey participants prior to the examination? Yes
 No

Was the information material and informed consent explained to the participant verbally during the examination visit? Yes
 No

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Did the participants have a chance to ask questions about the information material and informed consent before signing it?

Yes

No

3.1.3 Questionnaire administration

How were the questionnaire(s) administered? (Select all that apply.)

Self-administration (paper or CASI)

Interview (CAPI, CATI, face-to-face on paper questionnaire)

If computer-assisted method was used, which software programme was used?

In which languages were the questionnaires/interview available?

How many separate questionnaires were there (interviews and/or self-administered)?

_____ questionnaires

How long, on average, took it to fill in the questionnaire(s)?

_____ minutes

How many pages the questionnaire(s) had in total? (If applicable)

_____ pages

How many questions the questionnaire(s) had in total?

_____ questions

Was/Were personally filled-in questionnaire(s) checked for completeness by survey staff when handed over?

Yes

No

3.1.4 Health examinations

3.1.4.1 Blood pressure measurement

What type of blood pressure measurement device was used?

Automated device (non-auscultation method)

Aneroid sphygmomanometer

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- Mercury sphygmomanometer
- Other, non-mercury sphygmomanometer

Specify the brand of the used device

- A&D
- BpTRU
- Dinamap
- Meditec
- Microlife
- Mindray
- Omron
- Spacelabs
- Welch Ally
- Other, specify: _____

Specify the model of the device (e.g. Omron ic-10) _____

How many different cuff sizes were available on the field? _____ cuff sizes

Which were the sizes of these cuffs (bladder size or recommended arm circumference)?

Cuff 1: _____

Cuff 2: _____

Cuff 3: _____

If auscultation method was used, which side of the stethoscope was used?

- Bell
- Diagram

Was the room temperature recorded?

- Yes
- No

Was the room temperature comfortable?

- Yes
- No

Was there any disturbing noise during the measurement?

- Yes
- No

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Where the furniture in the room adequate for the blood pressure measurement? Proper chair for the participants and table for the measurement device.

- Yes
 No

How many blood pressure measurements per participant were taken?

_____ measurements

3.1.4.2 Anthropometric measurements

Which anthropometric measurements were included in the survey?

- Height
 Weight
 Waist circumference
 Hip circumference
 Bioimpedance (body fat)
 Head circumference of babies
 Other, specify: _____

Which device was used for height measurement?

- Fixed stadiometer
 Portable stadiometer
 Infantometer
 Other, specify: _____

Provide a brand and model of the used height measurement device.

Brand: _____
Model: _____

How often the height measurement device is checked using a calibration rod?

- Daily
 Weekly
 Monthly
 Each time the device has been moved
 Other, specify: _____

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For height measurement, were the participants asked to remove their shoes? Yes No

For height measurement, were the participants asked to remove their hair ornaments/head pieces such as hats/turbans if possible? Yes No

For height measurement, was the posture of the participants (back of the head, shoulder blades, buttocks and heels) checked? Yes No

For height measurement, was the position of head (ear canal in the same level with the cheek bone) checked? Yes No

For height measurement, were steps used if the participant was taller than the measurer? Yes No

For weight measurement, which kind of device was used?

- Fixed electronic scale
- Portable electronic scale
- Fixed beam-balance scale
- Portable beam-balance scale
- Baby scale

Provide a brand and model of the used weight measurement device. Brand: _____
Model: _____

How often used weight measurement device is checked using calibration weights?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Each time the device has been moved
- Other, specify: _____

For weight measurement, were the Yes

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participants asked to remove their shoes and heavy outer garments? No

For weight measurement, was the weight measured in underwear only? Yes
 No

For waist and hip circumference measurement, which device was used? Non-elastic measurement tape, max length: _____ cm
 Full body-length mirror
 Other, specify: _____

For waist circumference measurement, was the measurement done on bare skin? Yes
 No

If no, was the waist circumference measurement done over the underwear? Yes
 No

For waist circumference measurement, were the participant's hands hanging beside the body? Yes
 No

For waist circumference measurement, was the right measurement place palpated? Yes
 No

For hip circumference measurement, was the measurement done over the underwear? Yes
 No

For hip circumference measurement, was the measurement done at the maximum circumference? Yes
 No

For hip circumference measurement, were the participant's hands hanging beside the body? Yes
 No

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If bioimpedance or any other anthropometric measurement not mentioned above is conducted in the survey, corresponding check lists about the measurement protocol should be prepared for each measurement.

3.1.5 Collection of biological samples

Which biological samples were collected?	<input type="checkbox"/> Blood <input type="checkbox"/> Urine (24 h) <input type="checkbox"/> Urine (first morning spot) <input type="checkbox"/> Urine (random spot) <input type="checkbox"/> Saliva <input type="checkbox"/> Hair <input type="checkbox"/> Cell line <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify: _____ _____
--	---

3.1.5.1 Blood samples

Were fasting blood samples collected?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
---------------------------------------	---

If yes, how long fasting was required?	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 hours <input type="checkbox"/> 8 hours <input type="checkbox"/> Else, specify: _____ _____
--	--

For blood samples, which types of tubes were used?	<input type="checkbox"/> EDTA <input type="checkbox"/> Sodium Citrate <input type="checkbox"/> Lithium/Sodium heparin <input type="checkbox"/> Sodium Fluoride <input type="checkbox"/> Sodium Polyanethol Sulfonate <input type="checkbox"/> Without anticoagulant/preservative <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify: _____ _____
--	--

Were field blanks collected together with blood sample collection?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
--	---

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From which arm blood samples were collected (in general)?

- Right
 Left

During the blood sample collection, was extended use of tourniquet observed?

- Yes
 No

In which posture of the subject blood samples were collected (in general)?

- Sitting
 Supine

Were the blood samples processed (centrifugation, aliquoting etc.) already on the field?

- Yes, centrifugation
 Yes, aliquoting
 No

How were the samples stored on the field before transfer to the laboratory?

- Room temperature, specify temperature: _____ °C
 In a refrigerator, specify temperature: _____ °C
 In a freezer, specify temperature: _____ °C

3.1.5.2 Urine samples

For urine samples, which types of containers were used?

- Sterile container
 Polypropylene Container
 Other, specify: _____

Were field blanks collected together with urine sample collection?

- Yes
 No

Were the urine samples processed (aliquoting etc.) already on the field?

- Yes, aliquoting
 No

How were the samples stored on the field before transfer to the laboratory?

- Room temperature, specify temperature: _____ °C
 In a refrigerator, specify temperature: _____ °C

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In a freezer, specify temperature:
_____ °C

In case other biological samples such as hair, saliva etc. are collected in the survey, provide a corresponding check list for each sample type.

3.2 Day two: Discussions with survey coordination

These are the topics to be discussed with the survey organizes. It is recommended to obtain also the survey protocol but since it may be available only in the national language(s), it is important to discuss these issues during the visit. Sometimes it also happens that the protocol which was prepared during the preparation phase of the survey is not updated for all small changes which have taken place during the data collection. This may for example concern the timing of the survey. As an example, it may be that originally survey visits were planned for Monday-Friday between 8:00-19:00 but due the request by survey participants, additional visits were added for early mornings at 7:00-8:00 and for Saturdays.

3.2.1.1 Timing of the examinations

Does the field work phase of the survey take more than one year? Yes
 No

During which months is the survey conducted?

January
 February
 March
 April
 May
 June
 July
 August
 September
 October
 November
 December

In which calendar year(s) the survey is conducted? _____

During which days of the week, health examinations are conducted? Monday

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	<input type="checkbox"/> Tuesday <input type="checkbox"/> Wednesday <input type="checkbox"/> Thursday <input type="checkbox"/> Friday <input type="checkbox"/> Saturday <input type="checkbox"/> Sunday
--	--

During which hours of the day examinations are conducted? _____ to _____

3.2.2 Examination site

Where are the health examinations conducted?

- Health care centre
- Specially established examination clinic
- School
- Premises of the company
- Mobile clinic (bus/truck/etc.)
- At the home of the invitee
- Other, specify: _____

How many examination sites are there in total?	_____ sites
--	-------------

How many teams are simultaneously conducting the health examinations? _____ teams

3.2.3 Sampling

3.2.3.1 Target population

Define the geographical area covered.

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Does the sample cover rural/semi-urban/urban areas? (Select all that apply.)

Rural
 Semi-urban
 Urban
 Other area, specify _____

Covered age groups? _____ to _____ years

Which population groups the sample covers? (Select all that apply.)

Permanent residents of the country
 Citizens
 Population from hot-spots
 Pupils/students of a school/college/university
 Employees of a company/companies
 Other, please specify: _____

Does the sample include institutionalized persons?

Yes
 No

If yes, please define which institutions? (Select all that apply.)

Hospitals
 Homes of elderly
 Nursing homes
 Monasteries
 Prisons
 Other, please specify: _____

Possible exclusion criteria

Does not speak any of the official languages of the country
 Institutionalized
 Other, specify: _____

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3.2.3.2 Sampling frame

What was the primary sampling frame used for the survey?

- Population register (national or regional)
- Census list
- List of health centres
- List of patients from health centres
- List of schools
- Student list
- List of companies
- Employee list
- Post-code address file
- Other, please specify: _____

When the sampling frame was last updated?

- Updated continuously
- Less than 3 months ago
- 3-6 months ago
- More than 6 months but less than 1 year ago
- At least one year ago

Who maintains the sampling frame?

If applicable, what was the secondary sampling frame?

- Population register (national or regional)
- Census list
- List of patients from health centres
- Student list
- Employee list
- Post-code address file
- Other, please specify: _____

When the secondary sampling frame was last updated?

- Updated continuously
- Less than 3 months ago

- 3-6 months ago
- More than 6 months but less than 1 year ago
- At least one year ago

Who maintains (owns) the secondary sampling frame? _____

3.2.3.3 Sample size

Total sample size _____ persons

Is the sample size stratified (e.g. by sex, age, etc.)? Yes
 No

If yes, provide sample sizes by stratification units

	Age group 1	Age group 2	Age group 3	Age group 4
Men/ Boys				
Women / Girls				

3.2.4 Sampling method

Was the sample a probability sample? Yes
 No

If yes, which kind of probability sample?

- Simple random sample
- Stratified sample
- Cluster sample
- Other, specify: _____

If not, which kind of sample it was?

- A convenience sample
- A snowball sample
- Other, specify: _____

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Who (which organization) was responsible for drawing the sample? _____

3.2.5 Recruitment of participants

How is the first contact with the selected invitees/households made?

- Personal visit
- Telephone call
- Information post card
- Mailed invitation letter
- SMS
- Other, specify: _____

What is the maximum number of contact attempts during the recruitment process? _____ contact attempts

What are the subsequent modes of contact after the 1st contact? (Select all that apply.)

- Personal visit
- Telephone call
- Information post card
- Mailed invitation letter
- SMS
- Other, specify: _____

Are any incentives used?

- Yes
- No

If yes, which kind of incentives? (Select all that apply.)

- Monetary incentives incl. vouchers
- Compensation of travel costs
- Small gifts such as pen etc.
- Lottery for some larger item such is iPad etc.
- Health examination results
- Other, specify: _____

In which languages invitation material/phone calls etc. are made? _____

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3.2.6 Quality assurance procedures

Was the fieldwork personnel specially trained to conduct this study? Yes
 No

If yes, how many days did the training last? _____ days

Which topics were covered during the training?

- Obtaining informed consent
- Conducting an interview
- Checking of the self-administered questionnaire
- Measurement protocols for health measurements
- Collection of biological samples
- Handling of biological samples on the field
- Data protection issues
- Other, specify: _____

Is there specific calibration/check-up routines conducted regularly on the field (e.g. calibration of measurement devices)? Yes
 No

Are local/national audit visits conducted during the fieldwork? Yes
 No

Are the laboratories which perform the analysis of the biological samples involved in national /international quality assurance programmes? Yes
 No

3.2.7 Data management and data security

How are individual participants identified on different survey materials (questionnaires, sample tubes, etc.)? Personal Identification Code (national, regional, register specific)
 Study specific identifier
 Other, specify: _____

If paper questionnaires/recording forms are used, how are those stored on the field? In locked storage system (box, container, etc.)
 In un-locked storage system
 Other, specify: _____

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How is data stored in the central database?

- In relational database
- In MS Access
- In Excel
- In format of dataset for statistical programs such as R, SAS, SPSS, Stata
- Other, specify: _____

How many people have access to identifiable raw data?

_____ persons

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4 Site visit report outline

From each site visit (audit visit), a written report should be prepared. The aim of the report is to document observations and discussions during the visit, such as possible deviations from the HBM4EU protocols and for health measurements from the EHES protocols, and what might be the implications of these deviations for comparability of the results with other similar European surveys.

For preparation of the site visit report, the check list of issues to be observed (Section 3) should be used as a basis. For each point, observations are documented and a short note in relation to HBM and EHES SOPs is provided. Recommendations for improvements should be given at the end of the report, if necessary. The contents of the site visit report could be as below:

1. Time and place of the site visit (including who did the visit)
2. Observations of the fieldwork
 - a. Examination site, incl. location, access, signs to guide to the location, suitability of the premises for the purpose
 - b. Informed consent
 - c. Privacy of the participant during the examination and/or interviews
 - d. Questionnaire administration
 - e. Conduction of clinical health measurements
 - f. Collection and handling of biological samples
 - g. Data protection on the field
 - h. Interaction and communication of the fieldwork team with each other
3. Discussions with the survey coordination team
 - a. Time and resources used for the planning and preparation of the survey
 - b. Recruitment of the fieldwork personnel, number of persons in the fieldwork team and number of fieldwork teams simultaneously working on the field
 - c. Training of the fieldwork personnel
 - d. Selection of the examination sites (clinics)
 - e. Obtaining ethical and data protection approvals
 - f. Sample selection
 - g. Selection of the questionnaire modules
 - h. Selection of the clinical health measurements
 - i. Selection of the collected biological samples and planned analysis of biomarkers
 - j. Fieldwork logistics
 - k. Recruitment of survey participants
 - l. Quality control measures during the fieldwork and data checking procedures
 - m. Data management
 - n. Dissemination
4. Conclusions
 - a. Observed challenges and success stories
 - b. Possible deviations from the EU level standards
 - c. Recommendations for improvement

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5 Annex 1. Template for the consent to take photos during the evaluation of the fieldwork

Site visit photo CONSENT

I _____ agree, that the photos taken of me

on _____._____. 20___ during the survey examination can be used for

- the internal (non-public) HBM4EU site visit report,
- the public materials like the survey manuals, training materials and training seminars, presentations about the health examination surveys, press materials and other non-commercial purposes.

In _____ on _____._____. 20___
